

Magnetic and Spectral Behaviour of Semicarbazone Derivatives of Manganese(II), Copper(II), Iron(III) and Chromium(III) and their Antimicrobial Screening

AMITA SINGH^a, LALITA^a, RAJESH DHAKAREY^{*a} and G. C. SAXENA^b

^aChemical Research Laboratories, Narain College, Shikohabad-205 135

^bDepartment of Chemistry, R. B. S. College, Agra

Manuscript received 8 October 1993, revised 19 October 1994, accepted 4 November 1994

The semicarbazone derivatives of various transition metals have been investigated owing to their coordinating capability and pharmaceutical activities¹, but there is not much work on glyoxalic semicarbazone complexes of transition metals².

The present communication describes the synthesis and characterisation of Mn^{II}, Cu^{II}, Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} complexes with *p*-chlorophenylglyoxal semicarbazone (HL) and *p*-methoxyphenylglyoxal semicarbazone (HL').

Results and Discussion

The analytical and physical data of the complexes are given in Table 1. All the complexes are insoluble in water and common non-coordinating solvents but are soluble in the coordinating solvent DMF. The analytical data reveal 1 : 2 metal-ligand stoichiometry. All these complexes have high m.ps.

Magnetic study: The magnetic susceptibilities data (Table 1) indicate that all the complexes are paramagnetic. The magnetic moment values for the Mn^{II} complexes correspond to the presence of five unpaired electrons with a high-spin octahedral geometry, whereas those for the Cu^{II} complexes correspond to the presence of the one unpaired electron³. The values for Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} complexes suggest octahedral geometry. Slight deviation in magnetic moment values of the Fe^{III} complexes than spin-only value (5.92 B.M.) may be due to some equilibrium between low-spin and high-spin states⁴. Electronic spectral study further substantiates the geometry of the complexes.

Spectral study: The energies of the observed spin-allowed bands in all the complexes (Table 2) agree with the octahedral environment. The Mn^{II} complexes show a number of bands having fairly weak intensity. Since Mn^{II} ion has *d*⁵-electronic configuration the same type of energy level diagram applies whether the metal ion is surrounded by the tetrahedral or octahedral environment. So in the field of octahedral symmetry, there are three spin-allowed bands corresponding to transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4A_{1g} (\nu_1)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$ ($4D$) (ν_2) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ ($4P$) (ν_3) in order of increasing energy⁵. The spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes show three bands corresponding to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ (ν_1), ${}^2B_{2g}$ (ν_2) and 2E_g (ν_3) transitions are assigned to the distorted octahedral stereochemistry⁶. For the Fe^{III} complex a series of bands including *d-d* transitions and charge transfer indicating high-spin octahedral symmetry⁷. The bands observed for Cr^{III} complexes indicate octahedral geometry⁸.

The intensity of the $\nu_{C=N}$ band of all the ligands decreases upon complexation, indicating involvement of imine nitrogen in M-N bond formation⁹. Similarly the $\nu_{C=O}$ band for all the ligand shifted to lower wave number on complexation, confirming the coordination of the metal ion through the oxygen of C=O (glyoxalic) group¹⁰. However, the lowering in frequency is not that large because free ligand is conjugated to benzene ring⁹. There was lowering of 1 690 and 1 650 cm⁻¹ bands of the ligands, indicating the involvement of the oxygen of C=O (amidic) group. The ligands also display bands at 3 460-3 420 and 3 210-3 200 cm⁻¹ assignable to $\nu_{as} NH_2$ and $\nu_s NH_2$ respectively.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd. (Colour/M.p.°C)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					μ_{eff} B.M.
	C	H	N	Cl	Metal	
Mn(L) ₂ Cl ₂ (grey, 165)	37.31 (37.43)	2.63 2.77	14.46 14.55	24.50 24.61	9.44 9.53	5.91
Mn(L') ₂ Cl ₂ (Brown, 173)	42.17 (42.25)	3.17 3.87	14.68 14.79	12.39 12.50	9.54 9.69	5.94
Cu(L) ₂ Cl ₂ (Green, 176)	36.76 (36.88)	2.61 2.73	14.23 14.34	24.17 24.25	10.73 10.85	1.82
Cu(L') ₂ Cl ₂ (Green, 175)	41.51 (41.62)	3.72 3.81	14.48 14.56	12.23 12.31	10.08 11.03	1.88
Fe(L) ₃ Cl ₂ (Brown, 165)	35.17 (35.21)	2.53 2.60	13.61 13.69	28.84 28.93	9.02 9.10	5.90
Fe(L') ₂ Cl ₃ (Brown, 155)	39.67 (39.71)	3.59 3.64	13.81 13.89	17.58 17.62	9.17 9.23	6.09
[Cr(L) ₂](CH ₃ COO) ₃ (Brown, 178)	42.28 (42.35)	3.56 3.67	12.37 12.35	10.39 10.44	7.59 7.64	3.77
[Cr(L') ₂](CH ₃ COO) ₃ (Buff, 178)	47.89 (47.92)	4.70 4.76	12.83 12.90	- -	7.81 7.98	3.12

These bands remain almost intact in the spectra of the complexes showing their non-participation in the chelation. But slight displacement in these frequencies is due to the increased positive charge on the nitrogen atom arising by the donation of electron pair from the oxygen of carbazide moiety involved in chelation¹¹. The bands at 650–200 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of complexes appear to be sensitive to the nature of the metal. The bands appearing at 640–540 and 500–380 cm⁻¹ may be due to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ respectively¹².

Thus it can be inferred that the ligands are tridentate in nature having NOO donor system, and based on analytical, magnetic and spectroscopic data, an octahedral geometry may tentatively be assigned, although somewhat distorted, in which the anions are uncoordinated and remain outside the coordination sphere in all the complexes.

Antimicrobial screening : Agar disc diffusion method was used for antimicrobial activity. Seven-days old culture of fungi *Alternaria solani* and 24-h old culture of bacteria *Xanthomonas citri* used as test organisms, were grown on Czapeck agar media and nutrient agar media respectively. The fungi were grown

at $28 \pm 2^\circ$ and the average of three replications was recorded. The percentage inhibition was calculated¹³. All the complexes and ligands were found to be highly active against the fungi and bacteria. The concentration of the compounds used was directly proportional to the percentage inhibition. The metal complexes were found more active in all the cases than their corresponding ligands (Table 3), confirming the fact that chelation of metal to ligand increases the toxicity of the compound¹⁴. Cu^{II} complexes are more active than other complexes. The growth inhibition capacity of all these complexes follows the order : Cu^{II} > Fe^{III} > Cr^{III} > Mn^{II}.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. *p*-Chlorophenylglyoxal and *p*-methoxyphenylglyoxal (both Fluka) were prepared by the reported method¹⁵. Both the ligands (L and L') were prepared as reported earlier¹⁶ from the phenylglyoxals.

Preparation of complexes : An ethanolic solution of the semicarbazone (5 mmol) was added with constant stirring to an ethanolic solution of the metal chloride (2.5 mmol). Then solution of 1 g sodium acetate was added and the mixture was refluxed for 3–4 h on a

TABL 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA

Compd.	$\lambda_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹	Assignment	10 Dq	B	β
[Mn(L)]Cl ₂	22 727	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(4D)$	5 632	512	0.53
	26 315	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g, {}^4A_{1g}$			
	35 460	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(4P)$			
[Mn(L') ₂]Cl ₂	21 276	As above	6 348	577	0.60
	25 316				
	32 259				
[Cu(L) ₂]Cl ₂	12 820	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$	15 834	-	-
	14 285	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}$			
	15 384	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$			
[Cu(L') ₂]Cl ₂	12 195	As above	16 129	-	-
	14 492				
	14 750				
[Cr(L) ₂](CH ₃ COO) ₃	14 750	${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$	14 705	989	1.08
	22 727	${}^4T_{1g}(F)$			
	36 363	${}^4T_{1g}(P)$			
[Cr(L') ₂](CH ₃ COO) ₃	15 625	As above	15 625	912	0.99
	23 529				
	37 037				
[Fe(L) ₂]Cl ₃	13 157	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$	11 508	548	-
	15 267	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$			
	18 348	$T_{2g} \rightarrow n$			
	24 390	$n \rightarrow e_g$			
	30 769	$n \rightarrow n^*$			
[Fe(L') ₂]Cl ₃	12 658	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$	11 075	527	-
	15 748	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$			
	17 857	$T_{2g} \rightarrow n$			
	23 529	$n \rightarrow e_g$			
	31 746	$n \rightarrow n^*$			

TABL 3—ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF
THE SEMICARBAZONES AND THEIR COMPLEXES

Compd.	Concn. ppm	% Inhibition	
		<i>X. clatri</i>	<i>A. solani</i>
C ₉ H ₈ O ₂ N ₃ Cl(L)	1000	76.28	68.51
	500	67.01	62.43
	250	59.03	61.12
[Cu(L) ₂]Cl ₂	1000	91.37	80.00
	500	73.92	68.46
	250	60.74	63.17
[Fe(L) ₂]Cl ₃	1000	78.20	73.90
	500	72.70	63.50
	250	50.91	-
C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃ (L')	1000	73.50	65.24
	500	63.61	36.30
	250	41.73	31.32
[Cu(L') ₂]Cl ₂	1000	88.23	76.52
	500	75.07	71.27
	250	71.64	60.35
[Cr(L')](CH ₃ COO) ₃	1000	-	62.08
	500	65.02	60.34
	250	42.78	-

Average percentage of inhibition after 5 days of radial growth at different concentrations; Temp. = 28 ± 2°.

water-bath and then kept overnight. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol and ether and dried in air (yield 40–50%).

C and H were analysed at Microanalytical Section, C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method. Chlorine¹⁶ and the metals¹⁷ were analysed as silver chloride by standard methods. Magnetic measurement of the solid complexes were recorded at room temperature by Gouy's method. Electronic spectra (DMF) were recorded on a Spectronic-20D spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their gratitude to Dr. B. S. Kushwaha, Head, Chemistry Department, Narain College, Shikohabad, for his valuable suggestions.

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